

Onboarding in Variant-rich systems: Challenges and Strategies

Questions for completing the interview

In the context of this study we differentiate between two types of organizations:

- **An organization that develops a single software product/application** is one that develops an application, which may have changed over time to improve the interface or to add some specific functionality, but which essentially is the same application.
- **An organization that develops more than one software product/application** is one that develops several applications that differ (in functionality, etc.) from one client to another. We also consider in this category the case where only one application is developed and that, by means of permissions and/or configuration, is adapted to the profile of the different clients.

From what you said in the interview, we understand that your company belongs to the second category.

1. According to your experience, the methods, techniques, strategies, etc. applied in the process of incorporating a person into an **organization that develops more than one software product/application**, would they have any difference compared to those applied in the incorporation into an **organization that develops a single software product/application**?
2. The methods, techniques, strategies, etc. applied in the onboarding process, have they changed over the years in your company? In which sense?
3. Do you consider that the onboarding process in place in your company has evolved as the number of products/applications developed in your company has also grown?
4. The design or architecture or structure of the software system developed in your company, to what extent has it influenced the onboarding process? Has it eased or hindered the onboarding process?
5. Do you consider that there is any method, technique, strategy, etc. that could be applied as a result of the multi-product development carried out in your company that could not be used for a single application/product system?